

Phosphate Fertilization in Alluvial Soils of Allahabad Division. Interrelation in Water Soluble P, Adsorbed P and Olsen's P

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Fifteen alluvial soils of varying fertility levels selected from 5 districts of Allahabad Division were equilibrated with 0–20 ppm of P depending upon the fertility level and amounts of P in solution (W.S.P.) and in the sorbed state were determined after incubation periods of 24 hr and 30 days.

The soils of Allahabad and Fatehpur districts were found to be of high P fixing capacity and remaining districts of low fixing capacity category. The ability of the soil to retain or release P varied considerably. Usually low fertility soils have also low initial water soluble P but have high P fixing capacity. Soils with very low, low and high P fixing capacities alone will require high P application and there is hardly any danger of uneconomical return, whereas soils of high fertility status need little or no P fertilization. In soils of high fertility category, P in the supernatant liquid was more than 0.2 or 0.3 ppm even after incubation period of 30 days.

PHOSPHATE concentration in soil solution offers an easily determined index of phosphate availability. Only a small part of the total P present in soils is in the available form and, thus, an extremely small amount of P (often less than 0.1 ppm) is present in soil solution. According to Fried and Shapiro¹, P concentration in soil solution ranges from 0.001 mole/litre $\times 10^{-3}$ with average of 0.007×10^{-3} in acid soils to 0.03×10^{-3} in calcareous soils. According to Russell² a concentration of $10^{-5} M$ phosphate (0.3 ppm) in soil solution is optimum, $10^{-3} M$ has been regarded as high and $10^{-7} M$ as low concentration. Beckwith³ has suggested 0.2 ppm P in solution as a standard for comparative purposes because it was a reasonable value for a number of plant species. Fox and Kamprath⁴ obtained 95% of maximum yield when P in the solution was adjusted to 0.2 ppm.

Singh *et al*⁵ found a good correlation between phosphate sorbed value and crop yields at a standard equilibrium concentration of 0.3 ppm. Silva and Fox⁶ obtained 92 to 99% maximum yield when P concentration in soil solution was adjusted to 0.2 ppm. Ozanne and Shaw⁷ in their preliminary studies, showed that equilibrium concentration of 0.3 ppm P in soil suspension was the most suitable for optimum crop yields.

Thus, a knowledge of P adsorption characteristics appears to be important in making rational statements about P availability and phosphate fertilizer requirements. With this object in view, alluvial soils of Allahabad Division of varying fertility levels were equilibrated with P solution of known

concentration and the amount of P in liquid phase was determined. An interrelation between soluble P, adsorbed P and Olsen's P was worked out.

Experimental

Soils selected: The soil samples for the present study were collected from alluvial soils of Allahabad Division comprising districts of Allahabad, Fatehpur, Kanpur, Farrukhabad and Etawah. The samples were collected in such a way that soils of varying fertility categories could be obtained. General appearance of the soils, cropping pattern and previous soil test data served as a guide in collection of the samples from different fertility categories. In all 40 samples (8 samples from each district) were collected and brought to the laboratory for screening for a detailed study. From amongst the samples tested for screening, 15 samples (3 samples from each district) were finally chosen for detailed study. The soil samples were characterised into five fertility categories, viz. very low, low, medium, medium-high and high. The fertility-wise distribution of the soil samples chosen for detailed study was as follows: very low (3), low (2), medium (3), medium-high (2) and high (5) (figures in parenthesis denote number of samples of each category).

1.0 g soil was taken in a 100 ml conical flask. The soil : solution ratio was fixed at 1 : 20. The concentration of P added (as KH_2PO_4) varied from 0 to 20.0 ppm P depending upon fertility level of the soil. Lower concentrations were purposely added to P-rich soils. The initial concentration for each

soil was so chosen as to give final equilibrium concentration of P in the range of 0.1 to 1.0 ppm P. Few drops of toluene were added to suppress the microbial action during the above reaction and the flasks were corked. The samples were incubated for 24 hr and for 30 days. A 7 hourly hand-mixing in case of the former and weekly mixing for the latter was done.

After the lapse of incubation periods, the suspension was centrifuged for 20 min at 2400 rpm, supernatant liquid was separated using Whatman filter paper No. 40 and the solution analysed for P content by molybdenum blue method⁶ using sulphomolybdic acid reagent. The above estimated values of phosphorus (W.S.P.) when subtracted from the amount of P added to the soils gave the values of P sorbed by the soils. Olsen's P was determined by the procedure of Olsen *et al*⁶.

Results

Comparative data of Olsen's P, adsorbed P, W.S.P., and P in the supernatant liquid at two incubation periods is presented in Table I. Analysis of the results shows that P adsorption is gradual and a steady state is obtained only after a prolonged contact. 80-90% of added P disappeared from solution in very-low, low and medium fertility soils with few exceptions after incubation period of 30 days.

When the incubation period is small the soils of Allahabad district and its adjoining District Fatehpur behave alike towards added P and hence can be grouped under one category while the soils from Kanpur, Farrukhabad and Etawah districts in another category. The soils of the former category seem to possess high P fixing capacity and fixation of P takes place even when the soil contains as high as 24.8 ppm Olsen's P. The soils of the latter category show low P retention and a desorption is noticed in soils having Olsen's P as low as 4.0 ppm. In general, the soils with higher content of Olsen's P showed sign of desorption even at low dose of P application. These soils contain W.S.P. ranging from 41 to 78% of Olsen's P.

P in the supernatant liquid is found to be low in soils of high P-fixing capacity and values obtained are generally below the standard value of 0.2-0.3 ppm in the untreated soils. The soils of Allahabad and Fatehpur districts have a high P-fixing capacity. Therefore, P in the supernatant liquid even in medium to medium-high group soils seldom exceeds the standard value. Addition of P to the soils of Allahabad and Fatehpur districts at 4 ppm and 10 ppm failed to raise the level of P in the liquid phase beyond the said limit. On further raising the level of P application, P in the supernatant went beyond 0.2 ppm P. On the other hand, soils with low fixing capacities keep more than 0.2 ppm P in the supernatant liquid and when P is added at the rate of 4 ppm the level of P in supernatant liquid shot beyond 0.2 ppm. The soils of medium to high fertility status of these districts contained invariably higher concentration of P than the specified limit.

The range of P in the supernatant liquid in the soils of high fertility is from 0.45 to 1.91 ppm and the values for the unfertilized soils ranged from 0.45 to 1.52 ppm.

Thus, P in the supernatant liquid is directly related to Olsen's P in soils which is used as a criteria of soil category.

Relationship between sorbed P and P in the supernatant liquid at 30 days incubation periods :

Sorbed P : True picture regarding the retention of P by the soils of varying fertility categories is obtained at 30 days incubation period. Based on the findings of 24 hr incubation period, we grouped the soils from the districts of Allahabad and Fatehpur under one category and the remaining districts having low fixing capacity in another category. The above categorization holds good for incubation periods of 30 days also. In the first category, the retention of P varied from 90 to 100% of the added P irrespective of fertility of soils whereas in the second category the sorption of P varied with district and with change in fertility levels of soils. In Farrukhabad soils, the range of P sorbed was 62 to 95% in very low fertility category and 10 to 15% in medium-high fertility category. In soils of Kanpur, the P sorbed varied from 40 to 88% in low and medium fertility category and the range of variation in Etawah soils was from 88 to 95% for very low and high fertility soils. A sample (E-2) from medium fertility group of Etawah district showed abnormal behaviour and 65% to 14% desorption was noted.

P in the supernatant liquid : The amount of P in the supernatant liquid in the soils of high P fixing capacity was found much below the standard value of 0.2 or 0.3 ppm on incubating soils for 30 days ; the soils of high fertility are exceptions. In soils of low and medium fertility category from Kanpur and very low category of Etawah and Farrukhabad districts, the content of P in the supernatant liquid was found below the above limit. But the soils of medium fertility of Etawah and medium-high category of Farrukhabad districts showed marked high P in the liquid phase. The soils of high fertility invariably registered high P content in the liquid phase even at this incubation period (30 days).

It may thus be concluded that the soils of high P fixing capacities alone will require high P application whereas soils of high fertility level need little or no P fertilization. In case of soils of other categories (very low and low), application of P even at the increased rate will not be uneconomical. The rate of P addition has to be altered to get P in the supernatant liquid at 0.3 ppm level.

The soils of very low and low fertility status of Kanpur and Farrukhabad districts showed the sign of desorption at the former incubation but the adsorption was found at all the P levels of application on prolonged incubation. Similarly, 3 soils, out of the 4 soils where there was no sorption at 24 hr, registered sorption at the latter incubation period. It is thus clear that the soils showing no retention

TABLE 1—RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN OLSEN P, WATER SOLUBLE P AND SORBED P IN SOILS OF VARYING FERTILITY AT TWO INCUBATION PERIODS

Fertility status	Sample No.	Treatment	Olsen P (. g P/g soil)	Sorbed/desorbed P (μ g P/g soils)		W.S.P. (. g P/g soil)		P in supernatants (. g P/ml)		
				24 hr	30 days	24 hr	30 days	24 hr	30 days	
				5	6	7	8	9	10	
Very low	E-1	S	4.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	
		S+W	3.0	—	—	0.8	0.4	0.04	0.02	
		S+4P	5.0	3.6 (90)	3.8 (95)	1.2	0.6	0.06	0.03	
		S+10P	7.0	8.0 (80)	8.8 (88)	2.8	1.6	0.14	0.08	
		S+20P	10.5	15.8 (79)	17.6 (88)	5.0	2.8	0.25	0.14	
		F-1	S	1.6	—	—	—	—	—	—
	S+W	0.6	—	—	0.8	0.2	0.04	0.01		
	S+4P	4.2	2.6 (65)	3.8 (95)	2.2	0.4	0.11	0.02		
	S+10P	5.2	7.0 (70)	9.6 (96)	3.8	0.6	0.19	0.03		
	S+20P	11.2	10.0 (53)	19.2 (9)	10.1	1.0	0.51	0.05		
	FD-1	S	4.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	
	S+W	4.5	—	—	2.8	0.4	0.14	0.02		
	S+4P	5.0	0.2 (5)	3.8 (95)	6.6	0.6	0.33	0.03		
	S+10P	9.0	- 2.2 (22)	9.0 (90)	15.0	1.4	0.75	0.07		
	S+20P	16.0	- 11.4 (58)	13.4 (67)	34.4	7.0	1.72	0.35		
	Low	K-1	S	6.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
			S+W	6.0	—	—	1.2	0.8	0.06	0.04
			S+4P	8.0	1.2 (30)	3.0 (75)	4.0	1.8	0.20	0.09
S+10P			12.0	- 0.4 (4)	8.8 (88)	11.6	2.0	0.58	0.10	
S+20P			18.0	- 0.6 (3)	16.6 (83)	21.8	4.2	1.09	0.21	
K-2		S	9.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	
		S+W	8.5	—	—	3.1	0.4	0.16	0.02	
		S+4P	8.5	0.3 (75)	1.6 (40)	6.8	2.8	0.34	0.14	
S+10P		13.0	- 5.9 (59)	7.2 (72)	19.1	3.2	0.96	0.16		
Medium		A-1	S	14.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
			S+W	9.5	—	—	1.2	0.8	0.06	0.04
			S+4P	14.0	2.4 (60)	4.0 (100)	2.8	0.8	0.14	0.04
	S+10P	16.0	5.6 (56)	9.6 (96)	5.6	1.2	0.28	0.06		
	K-3	S	14.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	
		S+W	10.0	—	—	2.2	1.6	0.11	0.08	
S+4P		14.0	0.1 (2.5)	3.2 (80)	6.1	2.4	0.32	0.12		
S+10P	16.5	- 6.4 (64)	8.2 (82)	18.6	3.4	0.93	0.17			
E-2	S	13.0	—	—	—	—	—	—		
	S+W	12.5	—	—	8.6	7.0	0.43	0.35		
	S+4P	20.0	- 4.4 (110)	2.6 (65)	17.0	8.4	0.85	0.42		
S+10P	24.0	- (148)	- (14)	33.4	18.4	1.67	0.92			
Medium high	A-2	S	16.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	
		S+W	10.0	—	—	1.6	0.6	0.08	0.03	
		S+4P	10.0	2.8 (70)	4.0 (100)	2.8	0.6	0.14	0.03	
		S+10P	11.0	8.6 (86)	9.4 (94)	3.0	1.2	0.15	0.06	
	FD-2	S	18.5	—	—	—	—	—	—	
		S+W	20.5	—	—	5.4	1.6	0.27	0.08	
		S+4P	22.5	3.2 (80)	0.6 (15)	12.6	5.0	0.63	0.25	
		S+10P	30.5	- 13.8 (138)	1.0 (10)	29.2	10.6	1.46	0.53	

(Continued Table 1)

MISRA & PATHAK : PHOSPHATE FERTILIZATION IN ALLUVIAL SOILS OF ALLAHABAD DIVISION

Fertility status	Sample No.	Treatment	Olsen P ($\mu\text{g P/g soil}$)	Sorbed/desorbed P ($\mu\text{g P/g soils}$)		W.S.P. ($\mu\text{g P/g soil}$)		P in supernatants ($\mu\text{g P/ml}$)	
				24 hr	30 days	24 hr	30 days	24 hr	30 days
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
High	A-3	S	73.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
		S+W	63.0	—	—	30.4	30.70	1.52	1.51
		S+4P	60.0	- 3.8 (95)	3.2 (80)	38.2	35.0	1.91	1.75
	FD-3	S	38.0	—	—	—	—	—	—
		S+W	35.0	—	—	14.4	4.8	0.72	0.24
		S+4P	41.5	-15.4 (385)	- 0.4 (10)	23.8	9.2	1.19	0.46
	E-3	S	21.5	—	—	—	—	—	—
		S+W	16.0	—	—	12.2	7.4	0.61	0.37
		S+4P	18.5	- 1.4 (35)	3.6 (90)	17.6	7.8	0.88	0.39
	F-2	S	24.8	—	—	—	—	—	—
		S+W	20.4	—	—	9.0	1.6	0.45	0.08
		S+4P	26.4	1.2 (30)	3.6 (90)	11.8	2.0	0.59	0.10
	F-3	S	43.2	—	—	—	—	—	—
		S+W	32.0	—	—	25.2	17.4	1.26	0.87
		S+4P	38.0	- 4.0 (100)	- 1.8 (45)	33.2	23.2	1.66	1.16

Soil samples—A-1, A-2, A-3 From Allahabad district
 K-1, K-2, K-3 From Kanpur district
 E-1, E-2, E-3 From Etawah district
 FD-1, FD-2, FD-3 From Farrukhabad district
 F-1, F-2, F-3 From Fatehpur district

S = 1.0 g soil ; W = 20 ml water ; P = $\mu\text{g P}$
 (Figures in the parenthesis are percentages of the added P)

at 24 hr incubation, registered gradual adsorption with increase in P application at 30 days incubation.

Discussion

When a phosphate solution is added to soils, normally a major part is retained by the soil constituents and only a small fraction of added P remains water soluble. The reaction between soil P and added P appears to continue till an equilibrium is reached. Accordingly retention is likely to increase, leaving lesser amount of P in the water soluble form (W.S.P.).

Usually low fertility (either very low or low) soils have also a low initial water soluble P content but have high P fixing capacity. However, major part of added P gets retained by these soils, leaving only a negligible concentration of P in soil solution on prolonged contact.

However, if the soils contain high concentration of initial W.S.P., no retention of P takes place initially (first 24 hrs). These soils exhibit P retention only after an equilibrium period of 30 days.

The ability of the soils to retain and release P varies considerably. The high fertility soils do not retain any P in the beginning but do so after 30 days. This indicates that P is gradually converted to insoluble P compounds. Such transformations are not unusual. Even the low fertility soils, such as Farrukhabad and Kanpur district soils which do not retain any P at the initial stage of water-logging (at 24 hrs), begin showing retention after the incubation period of 30 days.

Thus the soils of Allahabad and Fatehpur districts can be grouped together with regard to their behaviour towards P application. These soils have high P fixing capacities and as a result only a small fraction of added P remains in water soluble form. The soils of Kanpur, Farrukhabad and Etawah district with low fixing capacities can be grouped likewise separately.

It can, therefore, be concluded that even increasing rates of added P to low fertility soils will not considerably contribute to W.S.P. whereas in high fertility soils, even the smallest dose of P (0.4 ppm P) will not be transformed into insoluble form even after 30 days. This indicated that the addition of P, if needed, can be practised without any danger of fixation of P and therefore economical use of P can be envisaged.

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